

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Public-civic-partnership survey guidelines

SPOKE N 4– Digital innovation toward sustainable mountain

DELIVERABLE D21

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s

	ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

COMMONS, URBAN COMMONS AND THE MOUNTAIN: A GENERAL INTRODUCTION

THE NEED OF HYBRID COMMUNITY SPACES

This deliverable aims at mapping the needs of public administrations and local communities based in Saint-Marcel, Nus and Fenis in Valle d'Aosta with regards the opportunity of using abandoned public buildings for organizing hybrid community spaces.

In particular, local stakeholders of the areas mentioned above are dealing with two main needs. On one side, they are looking for new models of local development which can overcome the seasonality which is strictly connected with tourism; at the same time, they are looking for innovative solutions for involving people temporary working in that sector, through the introduction of spaces where they can live and decide to stay even after the period of work. On the other side, local stakeholders aim at inventing public spaces, and namely buildings, where different activities can be managed, and communities can be involved in social and leisure activities.

THE INSTITUTION OF THE COMMONS AS A FRAMEWORK

In the last ten years, the concept of commons has become popular in social studies and political activism and in some countries domestic lawyers have shared the interest for this notion. Even if any (existing or proposed) statutory definition of the commons is still very rare, lawyers heard of the commons through the filter of property law where it has been quite discredited. In fact, approaching property law, many students of different legal traditions use to learn the origins of property rights starting from the “tragedy of the commons”, the “parable” made famous by Garrett Hardin in the late nineteen sixties. According to this widespread narrative, the impossibility to avoid the over-exploitation of those resources managed through an open- access regime determines the necessity of allocating private property rights. In this classic argument, the commons appear in a negative light: they represent the impossibility for a community to manage shared resources without concentrating all the decision-making powers in the hand of a single owner or of a central government. Moreover, they represent the wasteful inefficiency of the Feudal World.

This vision has dominated social and economic studies until 1998, when Elinor Ostrom published her famous book *Governing the commons* offering the results of her research on resources managed by communities in different parts of the world. Ostrom, awarded with the Nobel Prize in 2009, demonstrated that the commons are not necessarily a tragedy and a place of no-law. In fact, local communities generally define principles for their government and sharing in a resilient way avoiding the tragedy to occur. Moreover, Ostrom defined a set of principles for checking if the commons are managed efficiently and can compete with both private and public arrangements for managing the resources.

Institutionally, the commons became the tool of contestation of political and economic mainstream dogmas, including the unquestionable efficiency of both market and property rights in the allocation of resources. The research of new tools for managing resources has been realized in several experimentations that generally occurs at the local and urban level: scholars and practitioners use to define these experiences as ‘urban commons’.

This term refers to a series of experiences in which groups of active citizens organize themselves from the bottom up to take direct care of urban immovable goods, often urban voids or abandoned spaces, with the aim of managing and administering them through open and participatory governance mechanisms. In these experiences, the so-called commoning phase takes on fundamental importance. This is the phase in which a group of people demands the care, direct and participatory management of a given asset, emphasizing its importance for the satisfaction of the rights of the community or for its social cohesion. In this sense, they are ‘generative’, since contribute to improving the quality of life and the community’s welfare.

The main characteristics of these experiences can be summarized as follows:

- a) the presence of a good in need of care and regeneration because it is in a state of abandonment or to which, for other reasons, access by the community is denied (the asset is often in public ownership but this is not always the case);
- b) the presence of a community of citizens who decide to take care of it, adopting democratic and participatory procedures;
- c) the management of the good in order to offer services of a collective nature, directly related to the social cohesion of a given community or to the satisfaction of fundamental rights.

Although these occurrences, especially in their early stages, are largely based on informal dynamics, law is central to them. It is clear, in fact, that the self-organization of a community with regards to the use and management of an asset is, in the first place, an institutional matter.

In fact, since the assets mostly belong to public institutions, and especially to municipalities, communities are often engaged in collaborative processes with local administrations which are mainly based on a path of participatory co-planning on the shared use and management of the estate. Nevertheless, conflicts are possible to the point of communities taking the form of illegal occupations: in this case, paths of transformation from illegality to legality can be observed.

THE PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS

The sustainability of mountain territories can be strengthened by public-private partnership instruments. New regeneration models are achievable through social partnership. The principle of subsidiarity, which favors "the autonomous initiative of citizens, individuals and associations, for the performance of activities of general interest" (Article 118 of the Constitution), finds explicit reference in the forms of social partnership governed by the code of public procurement. Actions on the territories through collective practices has changed the idea of public planning of the regeneration of unused assets. New models of "community's action" on disused spaces and assets are regulated also in the municipal regulations. Before the amendment of 2023, the public procurement code provided for actions which included both the management of areas reserved for urban public green and buildings of rural origin and the creation of works of local interest through organized groups of citizens. Administrative barter, on the other hand, was envisaged to encourage the "participation of local communities in the field of protection and enhancement of territories", for "the cleaning, maintenance, beautification of green areas, squares or streets, or their enhancement through cultural initiatives of various kinds, actions of urban decoration, recovery and reuse with purposes of general interest, of unused and immovable areas". Social partnership includes today the following services (art. 201): "a) management and maintenance of areas reserved

for public green, urban and rural buildings areas intended for social and cultural activities, transferred to the municipality in execution of the conventions and implementation programming tools [...]; b) management, maintenance and enhancement of squares and streets or urban decor interventions and recovery of unused areas and buildings, to allocate them to purposes of general interest, on the basis of project presented by citizens, [also] associates [...], to purpose, benefit from tax relief directly connected to the activity carried out by the individual or by the association, or in any case useful to the local community of reference; c) construction of works of local interest, to be acquired with undisposable assets of the grantor, on the basis of project presented by citizens, individuals or associated, and at their expenses for the latest; the execution of the works is free of tax and administrative charges, except for the value added tax”.

These models define the sustainability of community spaces both for the recovery of real estate assets and for the offer of services on the territory. Today, not only individual or associated citizens can conclude social partnership contracts, but also micro-enterprises or small and medium-sized enterprises.

FROM PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS TO PUBLIC-CIVIC PARTNERSHIPS

A correct identification of the most suitable legal instruments to satisfy the regeneration needs of the territories requires first of all a direct comparison with the communities. The necessary involvement of local communities (individuals, associations, public administrations, etc.) in the definition of models based on the needs of the territory presupposes the identification of specific needs. To this end, the administration of questionnaires to all subjects potentially involved in the process of regeneration of the territory aims first of all to identify the real estate assets on which it is possible to intervene and the services that the community can create through the redeveloped real estate.

In the light of these premises and according to main objectives of the NODES project – Flagship 3, the questionnaire intends to collect and investigate the main carriers of collaborative processes of mountain regeneration. This aim will be achieved by interviewing public administrations, communities of citizens or the stakeholders involved in this project. The municipalities involved are Saint-Marcel, Nus and Fenis in Valle d’Aosta.

With regards to the questions composing the legal section of the survey for public institutions, we have composed them to:

- 1) understand if and how the idea of commoning and the creation of collaborative spaces are changing local policies of mountain regeneration and repopulation, producing an original legal framework and original procedures;
- 2) check if original legal models such as communities cooperatives and network contracts clash with public administrations' traditional models and paradigm, and in particular the impact of the idea of collaboration;
- 3) understand how the collaboration between public institutions and communities can be juridically formalized in a specific act;
- 4) investigate the capability of public administration to monitor the impact of commoning on the life of communities and neighborhoods;
- 5) collect the main problems and difficulties that public administrations are facing in their everyday application of these original legal institutions.

SURVEY AND TOPICS

A) DESCRIPTION

1. Public Administration and Institutional level

- Municipal/Local (indicate the city_____)
- Regional (indicate the region_____)
- National (indicate the state_____)
- UE
- Other: _____

2. Indicate the department or office appointed of the policy/initiative development

3. Provide a description of the policy/initiative (name; starting date; main objective)

4. Select the thematic area(s) invested by the policy/initiative: (multiple-choice)

- Civic Participation
- Culture & Arts
- Public heritage / Urban renewal
- Ecology / Soil consumption

- Economy
- Technology
- Tourism
- Sport & Leisure
- Employment & Entrepreneurship
- Production
- Education
- Housing
- Other: _____

5. Is this policy/initiative

- Part of your administrative practice (for instance, a regulation)
- A single experiment (for instance, a test): _____
- Other: _____

6. How many citizens are benefiting from the policy/initiative?

- < 50
- 50 – 100
- 100 – 300
- 300 – 500
- undefined number

B) LOCALITY

7. Does the policy/initiative involve the use of abandoned buildings?

8. Are these spaces part of the municipal patrimony?

- Yes
- No (it belongs to _____)

9. Describe how the buildings benefit from the implementation of the policy

10. Before the implementation of the policy/initiative, what was the condition of building

- In use
- Unused
- Abandoned / Ruin
- Other: _____

C) CITIZENS PARTICIPATION

11. Did citizens have a role in the definition of the policy/initiative? Which groups participated in its production? (in terms of gender/ age/ class)

12. What is the role of the citizens in the implementation of the policy/initiative? Have citizens responded the way you expected/ wished for this policy?

13. Have you created any particular legal structure to involve citizens in the implementation of the policy/initiative?

- Yes
- No

14. If so, please describe the legal structure and how it works.

D) FUNDING

15. How is the policy/initiative funded? (*multiple-choice*)

- Regular public contribution
- Public grant (*local, national, EU*)
- Tickets (specify _____)
- Private sponsorships
- Private donations
- Crowdfunding
- Other: _____

E) LEGAL ISSUES

16. According to your local/regional/national legal framework, have you encountered any obstacle in the introduction and/or the application of the policy/initiative?

- Yes
- No

17. If so, explain what kind of difficulties have you faced and how have you overcome them?

F) POLITICAL/FACTUAL ISSUES

18. Which are the main issues you are facing in the implementation of the policy?

- Lack of economic/human/administrative resources
- Relationship and communication with the target of the policy or the beneficiaries
- Relationship and communication with underrepresented communities, minorities
- Relationship with other public authorities (neighborhood council, region, state etc.)
- The demonstration and of the social impact of the project
- Other_____

19. Briefly describe the issue and how you are facing it